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CHIARA BENEDETTA BONI, FRANCESCA COPPOLA,
MARINO QUARANTA, FRANCESCA GIANNINI & ANTONIO FELICOLI

THREATS FOR WILD BUMBLEBEES CONSERVATION ON THREE
ISLANDS OF TUSCAN ARCHIPELAGO NATIONAL PARK

*Minacce per la conservazione di bombi selvatici in tre isole
del Parco Nazionale dell'Arcipelago Toscano*

Bumblebees are known to visit many flower species and are a fundamental element as well as keystone species for the maintenance of natural ecosystem and agricultural crops (KLEIN *et al.*, 2007). Land use, intensification of agriculture, climate change and the loss of suitable habitats are among the main threats that led 10% of *Bombus* sp. to be at risk of extinction (GOULSON *et al.*, 2008; RASMONT *et al.*, 2015). In addition, since the end of '80, in order to increase the efficiency of pollination in greenhouse crops (tomatoes, strawberries, blueberries) different species have been reared and commercialized through Europe and Italy, taking to the introduction of allochthonous subspecies into new countries leading to an alteration of the subspecies distribution range (INGS *et al.*, 2010; VELTHIUS & VAN DOORN, 2006).

In 2021 a survey of Apoidea fauna in the Tuscan Archipelago National Park was performed within the project "BIONETPARKS" financed by the Italian Ministry of Ecological Transition, to implement a monitoring network of bees and increase the ecological, biological and conservation knowledge status of these pollinators. The survey revealed three main evidences: (i) the first detection of a melanic specimen of *B. ruderatus* on Elba Island; (ii) the presence of *B. terrestris terrestris* on Capraia Island 100 years after its last sighting; (iii) the presence of hybrids individuals of *B. t. terrestris* X *B. t. xanthopus* on Capraia Island.

Bombus ruderatus (Fabricius, 1775) is a large, long-tongued and a late

emerging bumblebee species, distributed almost all over Europe (GOULSON *et al.*, 2005), with a variable coat colour (RASMONT *et al.*, 2015). The most common colour pattern is three yellow bands and a white tail. The individual detected in this survey was all black with a red tail, similar to *B. ruderatus corsicola* occurring in Corsica (RASMONT *et al.*, 2015). Despite *B. ruderatus* is facing a general regression in Europe, it is not declining, and it is not considered to be threatened (Least Concern in IUCN Red List of European Bees; NIETO *et al.*, 2014).

On Capraia Island *B. t. xanthopus* populations have been previously reported (MASI, 1933; RASMONT & ADAMSKI, 1995; RASMONT & QUARANTA, 1997; GENERANI *et al.*, 2001) while the last presence of *B. t. terrestris* dates back to 1917 (RAZZAUTI, 1917) and no hybrids have never been detected. At least two main hypotheses can be formulated on the detection of *B. t. terrestris* on Capraia Island: (i) *B. t. terrestris* has always been present on Capraia Island with a low population density, thus it has gone unnoticed by other authors, or (ii) its presence is the result of a more recent re-colonization promoted by several factors. Since no hybrid individuals have never been detected before this investigation, the second hypothesis could be considered the most reliable. The re-colonization event may be promoted by volunteer or unintentionally introduction as well as could be the result of a natural migration from other islands or mainland. According to FELICOLI (2021), no greenhouses are present on Capraia Island. For this reason, the hypothesis of a re-colonization as volunteer action for pollination purpose seems to be improbable. Ferries connect daily Capraia Island to Tuscan coast, where *B. t. terrestris* is present (INTOPPA *et al.*, 1995). Thus, an unintentionally introduction of *B. t. terrestris* individuals through ferries could not be excluded. In addition, a recent study performed in North Europe, described *Bombus* sp. mass-migrations phenomena. Queens were observed to travel over long distances (up to 200 km), even crossing large water bodies via active flight aided by favorable wind currents (FIJEN, 2021). Distances of Capraia Island from the mainland (60 km), Elba (33 km) and Gorgona (40 km) island are compatible with those travelled by bumblebees observed in North Europe. Therefore, *B. t. terrestris* could have reached Capraia Island migrating from the nearby islands or the mainland.

Since 2015, the subspecies *B. t. xanthopus* has been raised to the species level as *B. xanthopus*, endemic to Corsica and Capraia island (LECOCQ *et al.*, 2015), and in Elba island also hybrids occur (RASMONT & ADAMSKI, 1995; RASMONT & QUARANTA, 1997). Crossbreds between *B. terrestris* and *B. xanthopus* and between F1 hybrids were studied in captive conditions by DE JONGHE (1986) demonstrating that hybrids showed no limitation in fertility. On Capraia island, hybrids queens, workers and males were detected.

Presence of gynes and caste polyphenism within hybrids recorded on Elba and Capraia islands should be taken in account for an integrative taxonomic approach to assess the new status of *B. xanthopus*. In addition, within a conservation approach of *B. xanthopus*, introduction of *B. t. terrestris* for pollination purpose need to be avoided.

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Authors' Address — C.B. BONI, F. COPPOLA, A. FELICOLI, Department of Veterinary Sciences, University of Pisa, Viale delle Piagge, 2 - 56124 Pisa (I); email: chiarabenedetta.boni3@gmail.com francesca.coppola@vet.unipi.it; antonio.felicioli@unipi.it; M. QUARANTA, Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria, Centro di Ricerca Agricoltura e Ambiente (CREA-AA), Via di Corticella, 133 - 40128 Bologna (I); email: marino.quaranta@crea.gov.it; F. GIANNINI, Ente Parco Nazionale dell'Arcipelago Toscano, loc. Enfola - 57037 Portoferraio (Livorno, I); email: giannini@islepark.it